

Beyond De-Risking: Strategic Dependence as a Geopolitical Externality

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Abstract

Economic security has become a central concern in contemporary political economy, yet existing debates often focus on identifying vulnerabilities rather than explaining why strategically significant dependencies emerge and persist. This paper argues that strategic dependence should be understood as a geopolitical externality. Firms organize production and sourcing decisions according to private incentives that reward efficiency, specialization, and cost reduction, but some of the resulting risks are borne by consumers, governments, critical infrastructures, and society more broadly. Markets may therefore generate more strategic dependence than is socially optimal.

Drawing on the economics of externalities, the paper conceptualizes strategic dependence as a form of geopolitical market failure and reframes economic security as a problem of governing interdependence rather than reducing it. It develops a Strategic Dependence Index based on concentration, substitutability, and systemic impact, and applies the framework to rare-earth supply chains and advanced semiconductors. The analysis shows how strategically significant dependencies can be distinguished from ordinary commercial interdependence and identifies conditions under which public intervention may be justified. The paper contributes a theoretical framework for understanding the origins of strategic dependence and explores its implications for economic-security governance under conditions of geopolitical competition.

Keywords: economic security; strategic dependence; geopolitical externality; market failure; geoeconomics; economic statecraft; supply-chain resilience; political economy

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1 Introduction

Economic security has become a central concern in contemporary political economy. The COVID-19 pandemic exposed the fragility of highly optimized global supply chains, Russia's invasion of Ukraine demonstrated how economic interdependence can become a source of strategic vulnerability, and growing tensions between China and the United States have transformed trade, technology, finance, energy, and infrastructure into arenas of geopolitical competition. More recently, tensions surrounding the Strait of Hormuz have reinforced concerns about the vulnerability of critical economic chokepoints. Together, these developments have intensified debates about resilience, strategic autonomy, and the governance of economic interdependence.

In Europe, these concerns have increasingly been expressed through the language of de-risking. The European Union's Economic Security Strategy seeks to preserve openness while reducing vulnerabilities associated with critical technologies, infrastructures, supply chains, and economic dependencies that may be exploited for geopolitical purposes ([European Commission and High Representative, 2023](#)). Yet despite the growing prominence of economic security in policy debates, an important analytical question remains insufficiently explored: why do market economies repeatedly generate strategically significant dependencies even when their vulnerabilities are widely recognized?

Much of the existing literature focuses on identifying vulnerabilities, measuring dependencies, strengthening resilience, or analysing the use of economic interdependence as an instrument of statecraft. Less attention has been devoted to explaining why strategically significant dependencies emerge and persist in the first place. This paper argues that the answer lies in a form of market failure.

The central claim is that strategic dependence should be understood as a *geopolitical externality*. Firms organize production, sourcing, and investment decisions according to private incentives that reward efficiency, specialization, and cost reduction. Yet some of the risks generated by these decisions are borne not only by firms themselves but also by consumers, downstream industries, governments, critical infrastructures, and society more broadly. When concentrated supply chains create exposure to disruption, coercion, or strategic manipulation, the resulting social costs may exceed the private costs faced by market actors. Markets may therefore generate more strategic dependence than is socially optimal.

Conceptualizing strategic dependence as a geopolitical externality has important implications for economic-security policy. The challenge is not dependence as such. Modern prosperity depends on international trade, foreign investment, technological exchange, and cross-border production networks. Nor is the objective to eliminate interdependence through autarky or broad-based decoupling. Rather, the relevant policy question is how to identify and govern dependencies that generate systemic vulnerabilities whose costs

are not fully internalized by private actors.

The paper makes three contributions. First, it develops a theoretical framework that explains why strategically significant dependencies can emerge as a consequence of decentralized market behaviour. Second, it proposes a Strategic Dependence Index (SDI) based on concentration, substitutability, and systemic impact as a policy-screening instrument for identifying dependencies that may warrant public intervention. Unlike welfare-based measures of import exposure, the SDI focuses on the broader social and geopolitical spillovers associated with strategic dependence. Third, the paper outlines a European Strategic Resilience Mechanism that translates the externality framework into a set of policy instruments designed to align private incentives with public resilience.

The argument proceeds as follows. Section 2 situates the paper within the literatures on interdependence, geoeconomics, economic security, and resilience. Section 3 develops the theoretical framework and introduces the concept of strategic dependence as a geopolitical externality. Section 4 operationalizes the concept through the Strategic Dependence Index. Section 5 discusses the implications of the framework for economic-security governance. Section 6 outlines a European Strategic Resilience Mechanism. Sections 7 and 8 illustrate the framework through the cases of rare-earth supply chains and advanced semiconductors. Section 9 concludes by arguing that economic security should be understood as a project of governing interdependence rather than reducing it.

2 From Globalization to Geoeconomics

The contemporary economic-security debate emerges from the intersection of four literatures: complex interdependence, geoeconomics, economic security, and resilience.

The first literature concerns interdependence and power. Early work on complex interdependence emphasized that economic openness creates both mutual gains and political vulnerabilities. [Keohane and Nye \(1977\)](#) argued that interdependence does not eliminate power politics but transforms the channels through which power is exercised. This insight remains central to contemporary economic-security debates because trade, finance, technology, data, and infrastructure have become instruments of both cooperation and coercion. Similarly, [Strange \(1988\)](#) emphasized that structural power derives not only from military capabilities but also from the ability to shape production, financial, technological, and knowledge structures. Contemporary concerns about economic security can therefore be understood as renewed concern with how these structures generate both prosperity and vulnerability.

The second literature examines geoeconomics. [Luttwak \(1990\)](#) argued that the logic of conflict was increasingly shifting from military rivalry toward economic competition. More recently, [Farrell and Newman \(2019\)](#) demonstrated that global economic networks are asymmetric rather than flat, allowing states occupying central positions to exploit

chokepoint and panopticon effects. Economic networks therefore transmit not only market signals but also coercive power. Likewise, [Hilpert and Lohmann \(2026\)](#) emphasize the return of power politics to the market, highlighting how economic interdependence increasingly creates opportunities for strategic leverage. Recent work on economic warfare extends this argument by identifying the conditions under which economic chokepoints become effective instruments of statecraft ([Fishman, 2026](#)).

A third literature focuses on economic security, strategic autonomy, and de-risking. The pandemic, Russia’s invasion of Ukraine, and growing Sino-American rivalry have intensified concerns about excessive dependence on foreign suppliers and critical infrastructures. European policy discussions increasingly emphasize resilience, diversification, and de-risking as objectives of economic governance ([European Commission and High Representative, 2023](#); [Pisani-Ferry et al., 2024](#)). Recent research has also developed methods for identifying and measuring strategic trade dependencies ([Mejean and Rousseaux, 2024](#); [Consonni and Magerman, 2026](#)). While such work helps identify vulnerable sectors and quantify the welfare consequences of trade disruptions, it generally pays less attention to why strategically significant dependencies emerge and persist in market economies.

The fourth literature examines resilience, production networks, and systemic risk. Research on global value chains demonstrates how efficiency-oriented production networks can become fragile when exposed to concentrated sourcing structures, geopolitical disruptions, or systemic shocks ([Sheffi, 2007](#); [Gereffi, 2020](#); [Wieland and Durach, 2021](#)). Related work in economics shows that shocks affecting highly connected sectors can propagate throughout production networks and generate losses that exceed the initial disruption ([Acemoglu et al., 2012](#); [Carvalho, 2014](#)). Similarly, resilience research emphasizes that economic systems differ in their capacity to absorb, adapt to, and recover from shocks ([Martin and Sunley, 2015](#)). These studies demonstrate the consequences of concentration and interconnectedness but generally stop short of explaining why private actors may systematically underinvest in resilience.

Taken together, these literatures explain how strategic dependencies emerge, how they can be exploited, and why resilience matters. However, they leave a prior question insufficiently explored: why do decentralized markets repeatedly generate strategically significant dependencies even when their vulnerabilities are widely recognized? Existing scholarship typically treats strategic dependence as a geopolitical vulnerability, a resilience challenge, or a problem of economic statecraft. The possibility that strategic dependence may constitute a form of market failure remains comparatively underdeveloped.

This paper addresses that gap by conceptualizing strategic dependence as a geopolitical externality. Firms may rationally choose concentrated and efficient supply chains because they internalize private costs and benefits, while failing to internalize broader geopolitical risks associated with disruption, coercion, emergency public intervention,

inflationary spillovers, and constraints on foreign-policy autonomy. Economic security therefore becomes not merely a question of reducing dependence but of governing the externalities generated by strategic dependence.

3 Theoretical Framework: Strategic Dependence as a Geopolitical Externality

The central claim of this paper is that strategically significant dependence constitutes a geopolitical externality. The argument builds on the standard economic insight that private decision-makers may not fully internalize the social costs generated by their actions.

In environmental economics, firms may pollute excessively because the private costs of production are lower than the social costs. Pollution creates harms that are dispersed across society and therefore remain imperfectly reflected in market prices. Policy responds by making firms internalize the externality through taxes, regulation, permits, liability, or subsidies for cleaner alternatives (Pigou, 1920; Coase, 1960; Weitzman, 1974).

Strategic dependence works in a similar way.

Consider a European firm choosing between two sourcing strategies for a critical input. The first relies on a highly efficient supplier network located in a geopolitically sensitive jurisdiction. The second relies on diversified suppliers, alternative routes, inventory buffers, and redundant production capacity. The concentrated strategy is cheaper under normal conditions. The diversified strategy is more expensive but more resilient.

Let the private cost of sourcing be denoted by C_p and the expected disruption cost borne directly by the firm by R_p . A firm minimizing private costs chooses a sourcing structure according to:

$$PMC = C_p + R_p, \tag{1}$$

where PMC denotes private marginal cost. Yet disruptions can generate broader costs that extend beyond the firm. Supply interruptions may affect downstream industries, raise prices, require emergency public intervention, constrain foreign-policy choices, or weaken national-security capabilities. Let these broader costs be represented by R_s . The relevant social cost is therefore:

$$SMC = C_p + R_p + R_s, \tag{2}$$

where SMC denotes social marginal cost. When $R_s > 0$, firms do not bear the full consequences of their sourcing decisions. Private marginal cost falls below social marginal cost:

Figure 1: From efficiency to governed interdependence

$$PMC < SMC. \quad (3)$$

Under these conditions, decentralized markets tend to generate more strategic dependence than is socially optimal. The divergence may be reinforced when firms expect governments to absorb part of the costs associated with major disruptions. In such cases, the anticipation of public support can further weaken incentives to internalize geopolitical risks, increasing the likelihood of socially excessive dependence.

The magnitude of this divergence varies across sectors. In many consumer-goods markets, disruption may generate limited spillovers and R_s may remain small. In sectors involving semiconductors, critical minerals, pharmaceuticals, energy infrastructure, defense inputs, undersea cables, or digital networks, disruption may impose substantial social costs. In such cases, strategic dependence becomes a market-failure problem rather than merely a business risk.

This framework explains why warnings about supply-chain vulnerabilities often fail to produce sufficient private adjustment. Firms respond to risks that affect their own profitability, but they may not fully account for geopolitical risks borne by society. Economic security policy therefore resembles environmental policy in its underlying logic: its purpose is not to eliminate economic exchange, but to align private incentives with social costs.

The logic can be seen in maritime chokepoints, semiconductor ecosystems, pharmaceutical ingredients, rare-earth processing, cloud infrastructure, undersea cables, and other concentrated nodes in the global economy. Their strategic significance does not arise only from physical scarcity or geography. It arises because economic actors have organized essential flows around concentrated and politically exposed nodes.

Efficiency creates concentration. Concentration creates leverage. Leverage creates vulnerability. Strategic dependence becomes a geopolitical externality when the social cost of that vulnerability exceeds the private cost borne by the firms that create it.

Strategic dependence may involve several market failures at once. In some cases, firms may lack information about lower-tier suppliers or geopolitical exposure. In others, no single firm may have sufficient incentive to finance alternative capacity because the benefits of resilience spill over to competitors and downstream users. These information and coordination problems matter. The externality framework developed here does not deny them. Rather, it emphasizes the specific mechanism through which private sourcing decisions impose risks on actors who are not party to those decisions. This is why strategic dependence should be understood not only as a problem of incomplete information or coordination failure, but also as a geopolitical externality.

4 Operational Framework: Measuring Strategic Dependence

A central challenge for policymakers is distinguishing ordinary economic dependence from strategically significant dependence. Not every dependency creates a geopolitical externality. Excessive intervention can undermine specialization, competition, and the benefits of trade. A credible economic-security policy therefore requires a disciplined screening framework.

This paper proposes that strategic dependence be evaluated along three dimensions: concentration, substitutability, and systemic impact. These dimensions identify whether dependence is merely commercial or whether it generates broader social risks.

4.1 Concentration

The first dimension is concentration. Dependence becomes more problematic when supply is dominated by a small number of firms, countries, technologies, or logistical routes. Concentration increases the potential for disruption and coercion because alternatives are limited. Measures such as supplier concentration ratios, import shares, market shares, and Herfindahl–Hirschman indices can provide first indicators of vulnerability.

4.2 Substitutability

The second dimension is substitutability. Even highly concentrated supply chains may not create major strategic risks if firms can rapidly switch to alternative suppliers, technologies, or production processes. Strategic concern becomes more severe when substitution requires long lead times, high capital expenditure, regulatory approval, technological adaptation, or specialized know-how. Indicators include switching costs, time needed to qualify alternative suppliers, availability of substitutes, and compatibility with existing production systems.

4.3 Systemic Impact

The third dimension is systemic impact. Some disruptions affect only individual firms. Others spread across sectors, raise prices, threaten critical infrastructure, or affect national security. The strategic importance of an input therefore depends not only on firm-level exposure but also on spillovers to downstream industries, consumers, governments, and security capabilities. The key question is whether disruption would impose costs beyond the firms directly involved.

4.4 The Strategic Dependence Index

These dimensions can be combined into a Strategic Dependence Index (SDI)¹. The index proposed here should be understood as a *policy-screening SDI* rather than a structural welfare index or a precise quantitative measure of geopolitical risk. Its purpose is to provide a transparent and comparable framework for identifying dependencies that warrant closer policy scrutiny.

This distinction is important because recent empirical work has also used the term Strategic Dependency Index. [Consonni and Magerman \(2026\)](#), for example, construct a structural SDI from a nested-CES demand model and interpret strategic dependence as the welfare sensitivity of EU consumers to foreign supply or price shocks. Their approach is econometric and product-level, relying on estimated trade elasticities, love-for-variety parameters, and origin-specific taste shifters. The SDI developed in this paper has a different function. It is a policy-prioritization tool designed to identify cases where private sourcing decisions may generate broader social, security, and geopolitical spillovers.

The two approaches are therefore complementary. A structural trade-based SDI is useful for measuring the welfare cost of import shocks, while the policy-screening SDI

¹The SDI proposed in this paper differs from the welfare-based Strategic Dependency Index developed by [Consonni and Magerman \(2026\)](#). While their measure quantifies the welfare effects of import price shocks using a structural trade model, the present SDI is intended as a policy-screening framework for identifying dependencies that may generate broader social and geopolitical spillovers and therefore warrant closer policy scrutiny.

developed here is useful for identifying dependencies that may create geopolitical externalities and therefore justify public intervention.

The SDI also formalizes criteria that have emerged in recent policy debates on economic chokepoints. Fishman (2026) argues that true chokepoints combine concentrated control, limited substitutability, and asymmetric leverage. The SDI developed here translates this intuition into a policy-screening framework by focusing on concentration, substitutability, and systemic impact. The difference is that the SDI is not limited to offensive leverage or coercive capacity. It also captures cases in which private sourcing decisions create broader social vulnerabilities even when no state has yet weaponized the dependency.

Each dimension can be scored from 0 to 3:

- **Concentration** (C): 0 = diversified supply; 1 = moderate concentration; 2 = high concentration; 3 = dominant dependence on a single supplier, country, route, or technology.
- **Substitutability** (S): 0 = immediate substitutes available; 1 = substitutes available with limited adjustment; 2 = substitution requires significant investment or time; 3 = substitution is extremely difficult in the short run.
- **Systemic impact** (I): 0 = limited firm-level impact; 1 = moderate sectoral impact; 2 = significant economy-wide spillovers; 3 = implications for critical infrastructure, defense, public health, or national security.

The index is expressed as:

$$SDI = C + S + I, \tag{4}$$

yielding values from 0 to 9. A simple classification scheme is shown in Table 1. The additive structure is deliberately simple. It is intended to make the framework usable for policymakers and comparable across sectors, while leaving room for future empirical refinements, alternative weighting schemes, and sector-specific calibration.

Table 1: Strategic Dependence Index classification

SDI	Strategic Significance	Policy Implication
0–3	Low	Monitoring through ordinary market and competition-policy instruments.
4–6	Moderate	Disclosure requirements and periodic resilience assessments may be warranted.
7–9	High	Consider resilience stress tests, resilience obligations, targeted subsidies, and other policy interventions.

Figure 2: From strategic-dependence components to policy instruments

To improve transparency and comparability, each component should be linked to observable indicators. Table 2 provides illustrative examples.

The SDI should not mechanically determine policy intervention. Rather, it should serve as a first-stage screening mechanism that identifies dependencies warranting closer scrutiny. Sector-specific weights may be appropriate where particular dimensions are especially important. For example, systemic impact may deserve greater weight in defense, public health, energy infrastructure, and digital-network sectors.

The SDI should also be distinguished from purely trade-flow-based concentration measures and from structural welfare-based dependency indices. Concentration indicators can identify exposure to a small number of suppliers, but they may miss differences in substitutability and systemic importance. Structural welfare-based indices can estimate the consumer welfare effects of trade shocks, but they may not fully capture geopolitical spillovers, national-security implications, or the public-good character of resilience. The SDI developed here occupies an intermediate position: it translates the externality logic of the paper into a practical policy-screening framework.

Future research could refine the SDI through probabilistic risk assessment, input-output analysis, network centrality measures, firm-level supply-chain data, and historical disruption evidence. The framework should therefore be understood as an operational starting point rather than a final measurement methodology.

Table 3 provides an illustrative application. The scores are heuristic and intended to

Table 2: Possible indicators for the Strategic Dependence Index

Dimension	Possible Indicators	Potential Data Sources
Concentration	Import concentration ratios; supplier concentration; Herfindahl–Hirschman indices; country dependence shares; exposure to single routes or chokepoints	Eurostat COMEXT; UN Comtrade; OECD TiVA; firm disclosures; customs data; sectoral market studies
Substitutability	Supplier switching time; qualification requirements; capital intensity; regulatory approval needs; availability of alternative technologies; inventory coverage	Firm surveys; industry reports; sector regulators; procurement data; stress-test submissions; expert assessments
Systemic impact	Input-output centrality; downstream sector exposure; relevance for critical infrastructure, defense, public health, energy security, or digital systems	Input-output tables; national risk assessments; EU critical-sector reviews; defense and infrastructure assessments; sectoral vulnerability studies

demonstrate the logic of the framework rather than provide definitive empirical estimates.

Table 3: Illustrative SDI scoring across selected sectors

Sector/Input	C	S	I	SDI	Strategic Significance
Rare-earth processing and permanent magnets	3	3	3	9	High
Advanced semiconductors	3	3	3	9	High
Active pharmaceutical ingredients	2	2	3	7	High
Battery materials and components	2	2	2	6	Moderate
Mass consumer goods	1	1	1	3	Low

This scoring exercise illustrates the paper’s core distinction. Dependence on imported consumer goods may be economically important but not necessarily strategically significant. Dependence becomes strategic when concentration, low substitutability, and systemic impact coincide.

5 Why De-Risking Needs Economic Instruments

If strategic dependence is an externality, the policy response should not be limited to diplomatic language, voluntary corporate pledges, or broad industrial-policy ambitions. It should draw on the economics of externality correction.

The objective is not to eliminate dependence. Nor is it to maximize resilience regardless of cost. The objective is to align private incentives with public security interests. A policy focused only on reducing dependence can drift toward protectionism, blanket

reshoring, and inefficient subsidies. A policy focused on internalizing geopolitical externalities asks a more precise question: which private decisions create systemic risks that markets fail to price?

This distinction matters for three reasons.

First, not all dependence is harmful. Interdependence generates efficiency, innovation, scale economies, and political benefits. A strategy that treats all foreign dependence as suspect would impose large costs and weaken Europe's economic base.

Second, not all resilience is socially desirable. Redundancy, inventories, alternative suppliers, and domestic capacity are costly. The goal is therefore not maximum resilience but efficient resilience: the level of resilience justified by the expected social cost of disruption.

Third, strategic dependence is often produced by individually rational decisions. Firms may prefer concentrated sourcing because it lowers costs, improves quality, and simplifies coordination. Unless the social costs of vulnerability are priced or governed, firms will have limited incentives to adjust.

A credible de-risking strategy must therefore combine openness with targeted correction of market failures. It should intervene only when concentration, low substitutability, and systemic impact create risks that exceed firm-level costs. This approach is more compatible with open markets than generalized protectionism because it targets the externality rather than dependence itself.

6 A European Strategic Resilience Mechanism

If strategic dependence generates external costs, a policy framework that treats such vulnerabilities as measurable and governable risks may be justified. This section proposes a European Strategic Resilience Mechanism organized around five instruments: a Strategic Dependence Register, resilience stress tests, a Strategic Dependence Charge, tradable resilience obligations, and targeted resilience subsidies.

6.1 A Strategic Dependence Register

The first instrument is mandatory disclosure. Firms in critical sectors should report exposure to high-risk suppliers, chokepoints, single-source inputs, and jurisdictions subject to elevated geopolitical risk. Disclosure should extend beyond first-tier suppliers where feasible.

This follows a Coasean logic: risks cannot be priced, negotiated, insured, or governed unless they are visible (Coase, 1960). Transparency would allow governments, investors, insurers, customers, and firms themselves to assess vulnerability more accurately.

The register should not cover the whole economy. It should focus on sectors where

disruption could create systemic costs: critical minerals, advanced semiconductors, energy technologies, pharmaceuticals, defense-related inputs, telecommunications infrastructure, digital networks and other sectors identified through EU risk assessments. Information could be collected confidentially to protect commercially sensitive data while still enabling aggregate risk assessment.

6.2 Resilience Stress Tests

Second, firms in strategic sectors should undergo resilience stress tests. Banks are stress-tested because their failure can impose systemic costs. Critical supply chains can generate similar systemic risks.

Stress tests should examine exposure to sanctions, export controls, maritime disruption, cyberattacks, conflict scenarios, supplier withdrawal, and sudden demand shocks. The goal is not central planning. It is early identification of vulnerabilities whose consequences could extend beyond individual firms.

A firm that cannot survive a six-month interruption in a critical input should not automatically be forced to reshore production. It should, however, be required to provide a mitigation plan: alternative suppliers, inventories, contractual safeguards, insurance, strategic stockpiles, recycling options, or trusted-partner sourcing.

6.3 A Strategic Dependence Charge

One possible instrument for internalizing geopolitical externalities is a risk-based Strategic Dependence Charge. Firms maintaining exceptionally high exposure to strategically significant chokepoints could be required to contribute to a resilience fund reflecting part of the systemic risk associated with their sourcing structure.

The economic logic parallels Pigouvian taxation. Where dependence generates identifiable social costs that exceed the private costs borne by firms, a charge can encourage decision-makers to internalize part of those costs (Pigou, 1920). The objective would not be to discourage trade with any particular country, but to reduce excessive exposure where dependence combines high concentration, limited substitutability, and substantial systemic impact.

In practice, however, measuring the social cost of strategic dependence is considerably more difficult than measuring many environmental externalities. Geopolitical disruptions are low-frequency but potentially high-impact events, and estimates of their probability are inherently uncertain. For this reason, any Strategic Dependence Charge should be viewed as a supplementary instrument rather than the default policy response.

A more practical approach may be to link charges to observable indicators of vulnerability, such as SDI scores above predefined thresholds, rather than attempting to calculate precise monetary estimates of expected geopolitical damage. Such thresholds

could be established through periodic EU economic-security assessments and reviewed as technological and geopolitical conditions evolve.

The Strategic Dependence Charge should therefore be interpreted as one option within a broader toolkit that also includes disclosure requirements, resilience stress tests, minimum resilience standards, strategic stockpiles, targeted subsidies, and public investment in resilience-enhancing infrastructure.

The instrument should apply only when three conditions hold: dependence is highly concentrated, short-run substitution is difficult, and disruption would impose systemic costs. Revenues should be earmarked for resilience-enhancing public goods: diversification, emergency reserves, recycling technologies, trusted-partner production, secure logistics, and infrastructure.

The charge would also create incentives for private adjustment. Firms could reduce liabilities by diversifying suppliers, investing in substitutes, increasing inventories, participating in resilience pools, or demonstrating that their exposure does not create systemic spillovers.

6.4 Tradable Resilience Obligations

Fourth, Europe could introduce tradable resilience obligations in selected sectors. Instead of requiring every firm to diversify in the same way, regulators could define sector-level resilience targets. Firms exceeding the target would earn resilience credits. Firms below the target could buy credits or contribute to a resilience fund.

This instrument borrows from tradable-permit systems in environmental policy, where market-based instruments can achieve policy targets more flexibly when compliance costs differ across firms (Weitzman, 1974; Stavins, 2003). It is useful when the policy objective is clear but compliance costs differ across firms. Rather than imposing uniform obligations, tradable resilience obligations allow the market to identify where resilience can be produced most cheaply while still achieving a system-level target.

Tradable resilience obligations should be understood as one possible design rather than a universal solution. In some sectors, direct regulation, procurement standards, strategic stockpiles, public investment, or minimum diversification requirements may be more appropriate. The case for tradable obligations is strongest where policymakers can define a sector-level resilience target, where compliance costs differ substantially across firms, and where resilience contributions can be measured with sufficient reliability.

For example, one firm may be able to qualify an alternative supplier quickly, while another may face high technical barriers. A tradable system allows the first firm to generate credits and the second to finance resilience elsewhere. The result is a more flexible and cost-effective path toward system-level resilience.

6.5 Targeted Resilience Subsidies

Finally, governments should subsidize investments that generate positive resilience spillovers. Alternative suppliers, recycling technologies, strategic inventories, secure logistics, and trusted production networks may benefit entire sectors, not only the firms that finance them.

This connects to the industrial-policy literature on coordination failures, information externalities, and socially valuable investments ([Hausmann and Rodrik, 2003](#); [Rodrik, 2004](#)). Subsidies should be conditional, temporary, and linked to measurable resilience outcomes. They should not become permanent protection for politically powerful sectors.

The key design principle is symmetry. Negative resilience externalities should be priced through charges or obligations, while positive resilience externalities should be supported through targeted subsidies. Together, these instruments would move European de-risking from rhetoric toward incentive-compatible governance.

7 Strategic Dependence in Critical Minerals: Europe’s Rare-Earth Challenge

Europe’s relationship with China illustrates why economic security cannot be reduced to a simple question of dependence. China is simultaneously a major export market, a critical supplier, a technological competitor, and an increasingly assertive geopolitical actor. The challenge facing Europe is not whether to engage economically with China, but how to govern the risks that arise from asymmetric forms of interdependence.

Rare-earth supply chains provide a useful illustration. Rare earth elements and permanent magnets are essential inputs for electric vehicles, wind turbines, advanced electronics, aerospace systems, and defense applications. While mining occurs in several countries, processing and magnet production remain highly concentrated. The International Energy Agency reports that concentration in refining for key energy minerals remains very high, with China a dominant supplier for cobalt, graphite, and rare earths ([International Energy Agency, 2025a](#)). Recent export-control episodes have also shown that restrictions on rare earth elements and magnets can quickly affect downstream manufacturers ([International Energy Agency, 2026](#)).

Applying the SDI framework clarifies why rare earths are strategically significant.

First, concentration is high. Processing capacity and permanent-magnet production are heavily concentrated in China, creating a potential chokepoint for downstream industries. This corresponds closely to [Fishman \(2026\)](#)’s argument that rare earths represent an economic chokepoint because China combines dominant refining capacity with limited short-run substitutability and the ability to impose asymmetric costs through export controls.

Second, substitutability is limited. Building alternative processing and magnet capacity requires specialized expertise, capital investment, environmental permitting, and long lead times. In the short run, firms cannot easily replace these inputs without affecting production.

Third, systemic impact is substantial. Rare earths are not ordinary inputs. They support clean-energy technologies, digital devices, advanced manufacturing, aerospace, and defense systems. Disruption could therefore affect not only individual firms but also wider industrial and security objectives.

Table 4 summarizes the illustrative assessment.

Table 4: Illustrative SDI assessment: rare earths

Dimension	Illustrative Evidence	Score
Concentration	China dominates global rare-earth refining and permanent-magnet production, creating a major industrial chokepoint	3
Substitutability	Alternative refining and magnet-production capacity requires substantial investment, environmental permitting, specialized expertise, and long lead times	3
Systemic Impact	Critical input for electric vehicles, wind turbines, advanced electronics, aerospace systems, and defense technologies	3
Total SDI		9

Rare earths therefore score highly across all three SDI dimensions. In the language of this paper, this dependence generates a geopolitical externality because private sourcing decisions create vulnerabilities whose consequences extend beyond the firms directly involved.

The policy implication is not autarky. Eliminating dependence entirely would be prohibitively costly and economically inefficient. Instead, Europe should seek governed interdependence. A European Strategic Resilience Mechanism could require firms in affected sectors to disclose rare-earth exposure, undergo stress tests, develop mitigation plans, and contribute to resilience funds if they maintain excessive high-risk exposure. Public support should target activities with positive spillovers, including recycling, trusted-partner processing, magnet manufacturing, strategic inventories, and research into substitute technologies.

The contrast with many consumer goods imported from China is instructive. Such goods may be economically important, but they often have more available substitutes and lower systemic impact. Treating all dependence on China as equally strategic would dilute attention and raise costs unnecessarily. The SDI framework therefore helps preserve analytical discipline: the problem is not dependence on China as such, but specific

dependencies that combine concentration, low substitutability, and high systemic impact.

Viewed through this lens, de-risking is not decoupling. It is the governance of asymmetric interdependence under conditions of geopolitical competition.

8 Strategic Dependence in Advanced Semiconductors

Advanced semiconductors provide a second illustration of the Strategic Dependence Index. Like rare earths, they demonstrate how commercially efficient supply chains can generate strategically significant vulnerabilities when concentration, limited substitutability, and systemic impact coincide.

The semiconductor industry is particularly relevant because it occupies a central position in contemporary technological competition and economic-security debates. Advanced chips underpin artificial intelligence, cloud computing, telecommunications, defense systems, industrial automation, medical devices, and digital infrastructure. Disruptions in semiconductor supply therefore have consequences that extend well beyond the firms directly involved.

Applying the SDI framework highlights why advanced semiconductors constitute a case of strategic dependence.

First, concentration is exceptionally high. Leading-edge semiconductor manufacturing is concentrated in a small number of firms and locations. Taiwan accounts for more than 90 percent of global leading-edge chip manufacturing capacity, while TSMC dominates advanced-node production for many of the world's largest technology companies. The foundry segment itself is highly concentrated, with TSMC accounting for more than half of global foundry revenue and substantially larger shares in the most advanced process nodes (OECD, 2025; U.S. Commercial Service, 2025; Counterpoint Research, 2026). This concentration creates a critical chokepoint within the global digital economy.

Second, substitutability is extremely limited. Establishing a leading-edge semiconductor fabrication facility typically requires investments measured in tens of billions of dollars, highly specialized engineering capabilities, access to advanced lithography equipment, and lengthy qualification procedures. The OECD estimates that a leading-edge fabrication plant may require initial investments of between USD 10 and 20 billion before production can begin (OECD, 2025). Alternative production capacity therefore cannot be created rapidly in response to disruption. Even large public subsidy programs such as the U.S. CHIPS Act and the European Chips Act require many years before new capacity becomes operational.

Third, systemic impact is exceptionally high. Advanced semiconductors are general-purpose enabling technologies whose disruption would affect numerous downstream sec-

tors simultaneously. Semiconductor shortages during the COVID-19 period demonstrated how disruptions can spread from electronics into automobiles, industrial machinery, consumer goods, and broader manufacturing systems. Because advanced chips underpin both economic competitiveness and military capabilities, disruptions also carry significant national-security implications.

Table 5 summarizes the illustrative assessment.

Table 5: Illustrative SDI assessment: advanced semiconductors

Dimension	Illustrative Evidence	Score
Concentration	More than 90% of leading-edge chip manufacturing located in Taiwan; foundry production concentrated in a small number of firms	3
Substitutability	New fabrication plants require USD 10–20 billion investments, specialized equipment, and multi-year construction and qualification periods	3
Systemic Impact	Critical input for AI, telecommunications, defense, cloud computing, industrial automation, medical devices, and advanced manufacturing	3
Total SDI		9

Advanced semiconductors therefore score highly across all three SDI dimensions. Their strategic significance does not derive solely from their economic value, but from the interaction of concentrated production, limited substitutability, and extensive spillovers across the economy.

The policy implication is not autarky. Complete self-sufficiency in advanced semiconductors would be unrealistic and economically inefficient for Europe. The relevant objective is governed interdependence: diversification where feasible, trusted partnerships where necessary, strategic monitoring of chokepoints, support for critical capabilities, and resilience-enhancing investments in manufacturing, packaging, and design ecosystems.

The comparison with rare earths is instructive. Although the underlying technologies differ, both sectors exhibit the combination of concentration, limited substitutability, and systemic impact that defines strategic dependence within the framework developed in this paper. The SDI therefore provides a common analytical language for evaluating vulnerabilities across different sectors while preserving a distinction between ordinary commercial dependence and strategically significant dependence.

9 Conclusion

This paper has argued that strategically significant dependence should be understood as a geopolitical externality. While firms organize production and sourcing decisions according

to private incentives, the consequences of strategic dependence often extend beyond the firms that create them. Disruptions affecting critical inputs, technologies, infrastructures, or chokepoints can impose costs on consumers, governments, downstream industries, and security institutions. When these broader costs are not fully internalized, markets may generate more strategic dependence than is socially optimal.

This perspective contributes to contemporary debates on economic security by shifting attention from the consequences of strategic dependence to its origins. Existing scholarship has made important advances in identifying vulnerabilities, measuring dependencies, analysing economic statecraft, and developing resilience strategies. However, the question of why decentralized market economies repeatedly generate strategically significant dependencies has received less attention. The externality framework developed here offers one possible explanation by locating the problem in the divergence between private and social costs.

The paper has also proposed a Strategic Dependence Index based on concentration, substitutability, and systemic impact. Unlike structural measures that estimate the welfare consequences of trade disruptions, the SDI is intended as a policy-screening instrument for identifying dependencies that may create broader social and geopolitical spillovers. The illustrative applications to rare-earth supply chains and advanced semiconductors demonstrate how the framework can distinguish strategically significant dependencies from ordinary commercial interdependence.

The argument advanced here has important implications for economic-security governance. If strategic dependence generates external costs, policy should focus not on eliminating interdependence but on aligning private incentives with public resilience. The relevant question is therefore not whether dependence exists, but whether particular forms of dependence create systemic vulnerabilities whose costs are borne by actors beyond those making the underlying economic decisions.

At the same time, the framework remains conceptual and requires further empirical validation. Future research should examine whether dependencies identified as highly strategic by the SDI are systematically associated with greater disruption costs, stronger spillovers, or larger resilience challenges than dependencies receiving lower scores. Such work could draw on sectoral trade data, firm-level supply-chain information, production-network analysis, and evidence from episodes such as the COVID-19 pandemic, energy-market disruptions, and export-control measures. Future research may also explore alternative weighting schemes, probabilistic risk assessments, and sector-specific adaptations of the framework.

More broadly, the concept of strategic dependence as a geopolitical externality suggests that economic security should be understood not as a departure from interdependence, but as a problem of governing interdependence under conditions of geopolitical competition. Whether this framework proves useful ultimately depends on its empiri-

cal performance. Its value will rest on its ability to identify vulnerabilities that generate measurable social costs and to provide a coherent analytical basis for distinguishing strategically significant dependencies from ordinary economic exchange.

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